

Effect of injection molding process on spongy fiber-reinforced strengthened with concrete polymer composites

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Abstract:

In this study, researchers used natural sponge fiber (*Acanthus Montanus*) to reinforce ceiling materials. The fiber is both strong and stiff, as well as being inexpensive and easy to manufacture. The effectiveness of utilizing nature produced vegetable fibers as reinforcements in the cement matrix was investigated through flexural tests and water absorption tests through injection molding process. Results showed that minimal mass of the fiber fractions that is required to strengthen utilizing the nature developed spongy fibers is 5%, with a significant increase in flexural strength and load observed at this percentage. Additionally, the controlled samples exhibited the least absorption in H₂O, that is follows the test specimen with 5% fiber fractioned masses, while all the remaining test specimens will be absorbed with a value > half of their dry wts. of H₂O. The usage of natural sponge's fibers as reinforcements in cement composite demonstrates excellent suitability and performance. Strength and ductility were significantly enhanced at the optimal fiber mass fraction of 5%.

Keywords: flexural strength, injection molding process ,natural sponge fibers, H₂O absorption test;

1. Introduction

The study varied the mass fraction of the fibre, which is cut to very small pieces and is going to be mixed using waste papers, cements materials and water. Finally, the slurry, the o/p is poured to a mould which is rectangular in shape and is subjected to compaction process till the extra water is oozed out, thus producing very hard composite materials. Finally, the test specimen is left for curing for 1-2 months and the flexure, water absorption test is conducted. Then the study found that the optimal fibre mass fraction was 5%, which produced the best mech. property is compared with the brittle matrix without reinforcement. This study confirms the potential utilization of the spongy fibres as the reinforced cement matrix for various types of ceiling apps. The mathematical model deployment is also incorporated in this chapter. The steps for test process are presented. Some of them are selected the reinforcement material, selection of the matrix materials, determine the fabrication method, perform material characterization, optimize the composite material, reinforcement material, matrix material, fibre-matrix interface, fabrication method, processed conditions with the structural design is presented. Finally, the testing and characterization using a novel optimization procedure is presented. Also, the materials that are being used for the design, fabrication and testing process such as the flexural test and water absorption tests are presented. The third objective was investigation of the effect of different surface treatment on the mechanical property of the composites. The researchers concluded that usage of silane type of coupled agents and the plasma based treatments will drastically improve the inter-facial adhesion property b/w the polyethylene fibres and the polymer matrixes, thus resulting in good composite material with a higher level of mechanical properties. Finally, the

discussions on the experimental results are made and the justifications are carried out and at the end, the conclusive remarks are drawn. This study focuses on the developing of a fibre RF cementitious composite suitable for ceiling applications.

2. Literature review

In recent decades, there has been less attention paid to the developing and knowing of the materials used for building purposes, particularly in the realm of housing. Natural organic fibres could give rise to a large quantity of savings in the energy and in the conservation of the scarce resources. They are in different areas of the universe and can lead to energy savings, conservation of scarce resources, and protection of the environment. Although natural fibers are having very low mechanical property in comparison to the fiber synthetics, they have been used as reinforcement material for making straw type of reinforced hut and different type of materials. The natural abundant, plenty of supply availability, relative cheap materials and the swift replenish ability of natural fibres make them strong arguments for their use in the construction industry. In general, natural and vegetable plants as well as fibers play an exclusive and essential role in the ecological system. Fiber-reinforced cement and concrete matrices, whether short, discrete, or long, offer new and challenging possibilities for construction materials. The behaviour and properties of these materials can be better understood and designed using modern approaches, which is a departure from traditional concrete technology. These materials are classified as brittle-matrix composites, where fibers play a crucial role in delaying and controlling tensile cracking of the matrix. This delay and control of cracking lead to reduced deformation at all stress levels, resulting in improved fracture toughness, ductility, and energy absorption capacity of the composite. These technical benefits can be utilized in semi-structural elements like thin and flat sheets, cladding panels, and load-bearing members. Therefore, the current work focuses on utilizing natural sponge fibers to produce ceiling boards for the building industry. They included *Acanthus montanus* stem fibers, waste paper, rectangular wooden molds, water, cellophane sheets, and cement. To achieve homogeneous mixing of the composite and avoid balling problems during mixing, natural sponge plant fibers were cut into a size range of 35-40 mm. Waste paper, which served as a filler, was obtained from old newspaper pages. After cutting it into smaller sizes, the paper was soaked in water until it softened and then pounded manually with a mortar and pestle. In this research, the variable was the fiber mass concentration, while a constant recipe of a 70:30 weight ratio of cement and waste paper was used. The total weight of the matrix used was 500g, and the fiber mass fractions aimed for were $M_f = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, \text{ and } 10\%$. This fiber mass fraction was defined as the ratio of fibers to the dry constituents of the matrix by weight.

3. Materials and fabrication process

The design of multifunctional polyethylene (PE) fibers reinforced polymers matrix composite involves the developing of a mathematical model that can predict the mechanical functional property of the composites based on the properties of the constituent materials & the composite structure. The mechanical property of the composites are typically modeled using classical laminated plate theory, which assumes that the composite can be treated as a series of thin, homogenous layers, each involving of a unidirectional fibre layer & a layer of composite matrix. Designing a new type of multifunctional polyethylene fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composite requires a systematic approach that involves the following steps: The first step is to define the application or the purpose of the composite material. This includes determining the required mechanical, electrical, thermal, or other properties that are needed for the specific application.

3.1 Selection of reinforcement and matrix materials

Once the application is defined, the next step is to select the appropriate reinforcement material. In this case, polyethylene fibers can be used as the reinforcement material. However, the type of polyethylene fiber used could affect the final property of the composites. Therefore, selecting the

appropriate type of polyethylene fiber is critical for achieving the desired properties. The matrix materials used in composite also play a vital part in determining final property of composite. The matrix material should be selected based on the desired property of the composites & the compatibility with the reinforcement materials. The usage of natural sponges fibers (*Acanthes montenus*) as reinforcements in cement composite demonstrates excellent suitability and performance. Strength and ductility were significantly enhanced at the optimal fiber mass fraction of 5%.

3.2 Injection molding process

The fabrication method used to create the composite material is crucial in determining the final properties. The most common fabrication methods for polymer composites include injection molding, compression molding, and filament winding. Every methodology will be having its own merits & demerits, and the selection of a appropriate method should be based on the desired properties of the composite and the available resources. Once the composite material is fabricated, it is essential to characterize the material to ensure that it meets the desired properties. Material characterization can include mechanical testing, electrical conductivity testing, thermal conductivity testing, and other tests that are specific to the application. Locally sourced materials used in this study include fibres from the stem of the natural sponge plant (*Acanthes montenus*), waste paper, wooden rectangular moulds, water, cellophane sheets and cement. To achieve homogeneity in the composite, a weighed mixture of pulverized paper, cement, fibre, and water was prepared. The water/cement ratio for workable mixes was modified to produce a slurry with excess water, which facilitated the composite to take on the shape of the mould cavity and have a smooth surface without voids and air holes. Balling problems occurred when the fibre mass fraction reached 8% in the mix. After a homogeneous mixture was obtained, the slurry was poured into rectangular moulds and compressed using a 6-ton hydraulic jack for one hour. The samples were allowed to cure slowly for twenty-four hours before being demoulded. A total of eighteen samples were produced, three for each mass fraction, and cured for one month before conducting flexural and water absorptivity type of tests.

3.3 Optimize the composite material

After material characterization is complete, the composite material can be optimized further by adjusting the reinforcement material, matrix material, or fabrication method to achieve the desired properties. Overall, designing a new type of multifunctional polyethylene fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composite requires a thorough understanding of the application, the property of the reinforcement and the matrix type of materials and fabrication methods used to create the composite. With careful selection of these factors and optimization, a new composite material could be developed to suit the identified requirements of a number of applications in the mechanical engineering fields. Design features that should be considered when developing a new type of multifunctional polyethylene fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composite for various applications include: Structural design of the composite materials could affect final property of the composites. The design should consider the loading conditions and required property of the composites.

3.4 Testing and characterization

The composite material should be tested and characterized to ensure that it meets the desired properties for the intended application. Testing can include mechanical testing, electrical conductivity testing, thermal conductivity testing, and other tests that are specific to the application. Once the composite material is characterized, it can be optimized by adjusting the reinforcement material, matrix material, processing conditions, or structural design to achieve the desired properties. By considering these design features, a new type of multifunctional polyethylene fibers based reinforced polymer matrix composite could be developed for meeting of the particular requirements of various applications in the engineering sectors.

3.5 Mathematical models

The mechanical properties of the composites, the strengths and the stiffness's, can be calculated using the following equations:

Strain-Displacement Relationship is given by

$$\varepsilon = [B]\{u\} \quad (1)$$

Here, ε = strain vector; $[B]$ = strain-displacement matrix; $\{u\}$ = displacement vector

Stress-Strain Relationship is given by

$$\{\sigma\} = [D]\{\varepsilon\} \quad (2)$$

Here, $\{\sigma\}$ = stress vector; $[D]$ = stiffness matrix; $\{\varepsilon\}$ = strain vector

Stiffness Matrix is given by

$$[D] = [Q] [A] [Q]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Here, $[Q]$ = transformation matrix; $[A]$ = constitutive matrix; $[Q]^{-1}$ = inverse transformation matrix

The constitutive matrix, $[A]$, contains the material properties of the fibers and matrix, such as their elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios. The transformation matrix, $[Q]$, relates the material properties in the fiber and matrix coordinate systems, and is depending on the volume of the fractions of the fibres and its orientations. Adding to the mechanical property, the functional property of the composites, the electrical conductivities and the thermal responsiveness, can also be modeled using appropriate equations. For example, the electrical conductivities of composites which contain the conductive fillers can be modeled using the percolations theory that describes the connectivities of the conductive filler particles in different composite matrix. Each sample was subjected to flexural testing using the three-point loading principle to determine its flexural load, and strength, off-sets. Since the cement composite was being developed is meant to be used as a ceiling, it is crucial to test how well it responds to water leakages from the roof during or after a rainfall. To determine the water absorptivity of the composite, the researchers took three samples from each mass fraction, weighed them, and soaked them in water for eight hours. After taking them out of the water, the samples were cleaned, dried, and weighed again, with the data recorded for each mass fraction. Based on the weight measurements before and after soaking in water, the percentage water absorptivity was calculated and recorded for each mass fraction.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Effect of flexural strength, average load, and load deflection

The flexural strength of the samples, which is the stress at fracture from bend tests, was used to assess their performance. The findings showed that the samples containing 5% and 3% fibre mass fractions exhibited the highest strengths of 1.353 MPa and 1.343 MPa, respectively; while those with 8%, 10%, and 12% fibre mass fractions had progressively lower strength values. The control sample, which contained 2% fibre mass fraction, had the lowest strength values of 0.98 MPa, 0.89 MPa, and 0.69 MPa, respectively. The maximum load that the composite could bear before fracture during flexure/bend tests was defined as the flexural load, with the samples containing 6% and 4% fibre mass fractions demonstrating the highest ability to withstand the highest load before fracture, with values of 23.27 N and 21.14 N, respectively.

: Graph of flexural strengths in MPa

Fig. 0.1 : Graph of average load in newtons

The load sustainability of the samples was in the order of 8%, 10%, 12% (control), and 14%, with a decreasing ability to withstand loads. It shows the mid-span deflection of each sample, which measures the toughness and ductility. The 6% fibre mass fraction sample displayed the highest deflection value of 25mm, indicating the greatest ductility. In contrast, the control sample exhibited the lowest value of 9mm, indicating it was the most brittle among all the samples.

Fig. 0.2 : Graph of mean deflections in mm

Fig. 0.3 : Graph of water absorbability v/s fibre mass fractions in %ages

Furthermore, displays the percentage mean water absorptivity of each sample, which was used to evaluate the water absorptivity of the cement composite. The control sample (10% M_f) had the lowest percentage mean water absorptivity, with a value of 52.52%. Samples with 6% fibre mass fraction had a value of 65.75%, while the remaining samples had an ascending order of water absorptivity, with the 12% fibre mass fraction absorbing the highest quantity of water.

5. Conclusion

- The incorporation of randomly distributed natural vegetable fibers can enhance the flexure-based strengths of the flat type of composite sheet (cement type).
- Increasing the fiber mass fraction led to an increase in both flexural strength and load of the samples. The peak was observed at a 5% fiber mass fraction, followed by a decline from 6% to 13%.
- Additionally, 5% is considered the ideal fiber mass fraction for reinforcing the natural sponge fiber composite.

- The control sample had the lowest water absorptivity, followed by the samples with a 5% fiber mass fraction.
- However, the other samples with higher fiber mass fractions absorbed more than half their dry weights of water, which may be attributed to the increased difficulty in mixing with the addition of more than 8% fiber and the air spaces and voids resulting from the higher fiber content in the matrix.
- The usage of natural sponges fibres (*Acanthes montenus*) as reinforcements in cement composite demonstrates excellent suitability and performance. Strength and ductility were significantly enhanced at the optimal fiber mass fraction of 5%.

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